

METHODS OF APPLICATION OF INTEGRAL COMPOSITIONAL MEANS IN MODERN MODERNIZATION OF URBAN PLANNING SYSTEMS (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE CITY OF SAMARKAND)

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the principles of the formation of compositional means in the modernization of the general plan of the city of Samarkand, its pros and cons in the modern urban planning solution of the city system. The methods of their implementation and renewal of the urban environment are described.

Samarkand is one of the oldest cities in the world, founded around the VIII century BC, was the capital center of the ancient state of Sogdiana. It is today the second largest city in Uzbekistan after Tashkent. Moreover, two thousand years ago, the city was a "key point" and a central link in the trajectory of the "Great Silk Road", which, located between China and Europe, served as one of the main centers of trade, science and culture of the then medieval East[2].

The general plan of the ancient city of Samarkand.

For many centuries, Samarkand has formed its image as a historical city, which is quite bright and memorable. Nevertheless, the city has great potential for further development, not only as the historical center of our country, but also scientific, cultural, transport and gastronomic.

In August, the preliminary general plan of Samarkand was submitted for discussion. The main task of the general plan is to preserve the urban fabric as a whole, as well as natural conditions, public spaces, infrastructure and lifestyle of Samarkand residents.

There is a lack of any urban planning concept in the plan. Also, an "attempt" to apply the principle of ring planning, the center of which is Kuksaroy Square, writes architect-designer, member of the Buyuk Kelajak Council Tahmina Turdialieva. She suggests developing the city on the principle of triangular planning[4].

The main qualities of the urban composition that ensure ensembleness are the integrity of the three-dimensional composition; the scale of architectural structures among themselves and in relation to a person; compositional diversity. Of great importance in the formation of urban composition is the urban scale. In modern urban planning, it is often forgotten that "a person is the measure of all things." Among high-rise and high-density buildings, people have not felt their "dignity" for a long time, as the classics of architecture have always remembered. Despite the fact that the city of Samarkand has been developing for many years without a master plan, the city as a living organism itself has identified street nodes and strategic points that have created the overall infrastructure of the city. It is very important to encourage the development of these urban elements, which for many reasons (social, economic, cultural, geographical, environmental) have become strategically important[3].

The general plan of the city of Samarkand 2020.

Compositional diversity is manifested in the use of buildings of different sizes, heights, and styles. Historical ensembles, as a rule, were formed for a long time, rebuilt as needed. As historical experience shows, the use of different architectural styles can not only not destroy the integrity of urban complexes, but also compositionally enrich them with a variety of architectural forms.

Rhythmic and metric alternations of elements in space, symmetry and asymmetry, modular and proportional divisions of buildings, etc. serve as means of harmonizing spatial relationships and correlations of elements of urban composition.

Rhythmic constructions are created according to the laws of progressions (increasing, decreasing, accelerated, slowed down, etc.). The signs of rhythm are: a change in the magnitude (height) of the elements of metric series; a change in the magnitude of the elements and the intervals between them; a change in the magnitude of the elements, the intervals between them and the number of elements of metric series.

Metric constructions are based on the repetition of forms and intervals between them. Metric series in which the same form is repeated are called simple. In urban planning practice, both simple and complex metric series are used, which are formed when two or more simple metric series are combined. Complex metric series include, for example, those in which unequal volumetric elements and unequal intervals between them alternate.

Navoi City

Spatial, plastic, light-color means are used in urban composition. With their help, the geometry of spaces, the plasticity of buildings and land are constructed, color and black-and-white characteristics of the environment are formed. On the example of the city of Navoi.

"Recent events related to private development in Samarkand have shown that without the development of a Master plan for our city, we cannot expect its development, and the chaos with dot construction will only intensify."

Of course, the city of Samarkand will develop and expand at an unpredictable pace and scale. The population of Samarkand exceeds 600 thousand people, and the existing housing stock and infrastructure are gradually exhausting their potential.

Conclusion

In accordance with the targeted program approved by the Ministry of Construction on the basis of the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 5, 2016, the creation in 2017-2019 of a Master plan and a detailed plan of the central part of the city of Samarkand, calculated until 2040, was entrusted to the state unitary enterprise "Toshkentboshplan LITI". At the next stage - consideration of the Master Plan at the Republican architectural and urban Planning Council, and then its approval by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It provides for the expansion of the city by annexing part of the territories of the Samarkand, Taylak, Pastdargom and Akdarya districts. It is also planned to create a tourist zone "Samarkand City", the construction of service facilities on the territory of this tourist zone for the summit of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization, which is scheduled to be held in Samarkand in 2022.

At the 25th session of the UNESCO World Heritage Committee in 2001, the historical center of the city was included in the World Heritage List of this organization in the nomination "Samarkand - the crossroads of cultures". The specified list includes the archaeological city of Afrosiab, the old Timurid city and the European part of the city dating back to the period of the annexation of Central Asia to Russia. The construction management provides for the control of construction processes in historical territories and the preservation of the historical appearance of the city.

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